

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING

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Abstract:

Social Media is rapidly emerging nowadays as the next big frontier for customer interaction .In this modern lifestyle there are millions of customer interactions taking place in our day-day life on social media sites. Such as Twitter, Youtube, Instagram etc,... ,and more number of customers support online communities .Some of the core pillars of social media are Advertising, Analytical and Reporting, Engagement and Listening, Publishing and Planning, Social strategy. Social Media is one of the innovative tools that collects a million of people around the globe. The main purpose of the social media marketing is to increase a brand's visibility and to build a brand. And other main purpose of social media marketing is to build a friendly relationship with the customers and to communicate with the potential customers. In this, Content strategy is the best strategy we can use to interact and engage the customers. Major findings are Facebook and Instagram are the best top two social media platforms used by the customers in the shorter period of time this has been changed by the last two years.

This paper gives us a powerful insights of Social Media marketing. The study develops an innovative outlook for the investigation on Social Media Marketing.

Keywords:- *Methodology, Quantitative research, Core pillar, Purpose, Findings, Powerful insights.*

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Introduction:

Social media marketing (SMM) is an art of producing traffic to site for generating business through online social group In the current era of technology , when the new technological advance are taking place at every walk of our lives. We are trying to show how these social media marketing tools are impacting the youth perspective. Now a days the number of internet user around the world is more constantly growing. The following report gives analysis about the consumption of social media and overall help us to develop an understand how the social media is proving to be BOON OR BANE to the society.

What Is Social Media Marketing (SSM):

Social media marketing (SSM) is the use of social media websites and social networks to market a company's products and service.

History of Social Media:

Social media build their plant in 1970 and first email were sent in 1971. The first online Bulletin Board System BBS

came in 1979 , After that in 1980- made first commercial service and introduced online chat system. FACEBOOK was launched only for Harvard student in 2004. Then in 2005 YouTube was launched. At 2011 FACEBOOK surprised with 600 million active users .

Literature Review:

The literature review of Palmer and Lewis (2009) titled an experiential, social network-based approach to direct marketing and Ralf Beuker and Erik Roscam Abbing (2010) paper titled Two Faces of Social Media.

Chi (2011, 46) defines **social media marketing** as a “connection between brands and consumers, [while] offering a personal channel and currency for user centered networking and **social** interaction.” The tools and approaches for communicating with customers have changed greatly with the emergence of **social media**.

Aim & Objective:

1. To find out the various method of social media tools.
2. To study the effective implementation of social media marketing for different type of business.
3. To suggest strategies to bridge the gap between the expectation and performance to improve the social media effectiveness.
4. To find out the trust level over the information received from the social networking sites.

Types of Social Media Marketing:

1. FACEBOOK:

More the 2 billion people monthly uses facebook. It provides advertisers with an unparalleled opportunity to reach virtually everyone and anyone. They allow a product to provide photos, short videos and description.

2. TWITTER:

Twitter is popular micro blogging site amongst the celebrities and politicians. The message or tweet can be personal thoughts, news & pictures, links, brand & product ,service links. It helps to project what your company is doing and accessing a large audience , where your tweet can promote products and events.

3. INSTAGRAM:

Instagram is very popular social media platform using for marketing the product by adding photos and short videos and it is recently purchased by facebook . The product can upload videos and photos and can link with other social platform and invite people to click for favourite one. Promote the photo sharing contests of different themes, discount offer codes, invite testimonial and use hashtags.

4. YOUTUBE:

YouTube has 1 billion registered users at which videos are viewed 4 billion times per day is largest media sharing site in the world. This platform has been used to entertain ,educate, share thoughts, provoke, and inspire people. It is accessible to everyone, with or without registering an account. Younger generations like Gen Z and Millennials are almost entirely on YouTube but its estimated that 50% of the older generation are also on the platform .

5. BLOG

Blogs can be updated on a frequent basis. Blogs can also be regularly developed for a variety of different purposes. Share and link to certain blog post that may interest your social media followers.

DOES YOUR ONLINE MARKETING STRATEGY MEASURE UP

1. Strategy- Have a strategy with clear aims and goal.

2. Customer – know your customer base and your customer destination.
3. Social media – embrace social media (Google , facebook, instagram, youTube)
4. Monitor & measure – monitor & measure your website hits and online sale rate .

Benefits Of Social Media Marketing (SSM):

1. SMM Consistently Warms Up A New Audience For Your Business:

Social platform like facebook, YouTube , instagram, allows you to connect with the customer and warm then up.
Eg: creating an interesting short video ad will create people to know more about the product.

2. SMM Builds Stronger Relationship With Customer:

Successful brand engage and connect with their social platform customers to build lasting relationship. Rather than focusing on selling your product or service you can make your social media audience followers questions about the brand product or share some feedback this could help you to make easier for your customers.

3. SMM Cost Effective:

One of the most cost effective and diverse way of promoting a business is social media marketing . It does not cost anything to create a brand profile in the social media networking site. The cost is relatively low as compared to other advertising platform if in case you want to run a paid campaign to make your content boost. The most important benefit is that it will allows you to tract your performance level and find tune your strategies by using real time data.

4. SMM – Leg Up On Competitors:

Tracking the ideas of your competitors are up to should be a key part of your social networking strategy. You can notice what are all ideas and techniques are working for your competitors. Example: if Instagram and YouTube ads are generating good result for your competitors you should also try this social platform.

5. SMM –Generates More Leads And Conversion

Social platform like YouTube, Instagram, facebook, twitter are allows companies to generate leads we can use a mix of paid and organic tactics to boost conversion. Content compelling may lead your social media follows to your company's website and turn then into loyal customers.

Methodology:

First we will review the literature with potential of social media as the marketing tool in the business . The secondary data collection method was used in research.

Secondary Data: the secondary data will be collected the internet content , blogs, research paper, books , and journals

1. Benefits Of Social Media Marketing:

The above chart shows the significant 93% of marketers indicated that their social media effort have generated more exposure for their business . The second more benefit is increased traffic with positive result of 87%.

1. B2B VS B2C Platform Use:

How does the way marketers are using social platforms different B2C VS B2B?

B2B – Business to Business B2C – Business to consumer

Most of the business to consumer(B2C) marketers are focused on facebook. Interestingly, B2C reduced their use of twitter in 2018 down from 62% and increase the use of instagram up from 72% in 2018.

Most business to business (B2B) marketers also use facebook and not surprisingly a significant percentage use of LinkedIn. What is surprising to me is the choice of facebook over LinkedIn. B2B marketers have also increase their use of instagram in the last year up from 57% in 2018

2. Social Media Platform Marketers Want To Learn More About

We are asked marketers to identify which social media platforms they want to learn more about. Instagram surpassed facebook for first time. Interesting about facebook marketing dropped to 69% from 79% in 2018. Messenger bots dropped to 45% from 70% in 2018. B2C marketers are more interested about instagram (76% B2C vs. 65%B2B).

FINDING:

1. From the above chart we find the benefits of social media marketing.
2. Active and effective use of social media in marketing.
3. The social media platforms different between B2B AND B2C.
4. Which social media platform should used for marketers?

Challenges For Organisation In Using Social Media Marketing:

Social media networking platform also offers some challenges to the business . challenges such as invasion of user privacy, lack of e-commerce abilities, aggressive ads, lack of brand control and certain legal pitfalls, can be major disruptions to the social platforms. Some social media platform do not give proper attention to their blogs due to this some people start using negative or abuse language for one another this will create bad or negative impression about the business.

CONCLUSION:

Using social media networking we can reach the users who are interested in their products. Each post that is shared will be introduced to the new network of individual, which can lead them to become a loyal customers and the more people who know about your business, better. The organization need to realize tangible business benefits, they need to find better way to plan, manage and measure their social networking effect.

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